

Comparative Analysis of Clinical and Neurological Manifestations of Repeated Mild Traumatic Brain Injury

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Abstract:

Relevance. Every year, 1.7 million people around the world suffer from various levels of myanng damage. 200 out of every 10.000 people take a serious juncture. And 2000 patients are provided with surgical care. A mild degree of brain damage is usually 2 to 3 times more common in men than in women. 78.8% of all listed brain injuries are male, 21.2% are female. The state of death from brain damage is 34%.

Despite the efforts of the state to develop innovative technologies in the field of medicine, the proportion of disabled people with diseases of the nervous system in childhood is 1.5-4.5 % of the total child population [1.4.7]. The untimely detection of structural intracranial changes in children is explained by the significant variability of clinical symptoms and the severity of pathology [2.3.9]. Special diagnostic difficulties in assessing the neurological condition occur with an atypical clinical picture or at the stage of preclinical manifestations of the disease [4.5.8]. Thus, according to the literature, the frequency of structural intracranial changes (SVI) in mild traumatic brain injury (TBI) in children, it is 1.0-6.3%, and 0.2-0.8% of them are severe [6.9.10].

The majority of patients who have received a mild degree of

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brain damage are the most active 15-24 years of age. Among young people and adolescents, neurosurgeons predominate in 80 - 85% of brain damage, while in patients over 40 years of age, eating and squeezing of the head brain predominate. Among all types of injuries, brain injuries account for about 30-50% of cases. One of the most important causes that lead to the death and disability of patients with brain damage is palpation. High morbidity as a result of a head injury is first and foremost among the working-class youth of the population. It has been established that damage to the brain of the head can cause an outbreak of degenerative diseases of the brain (Sitel D.A. Ananov K.S. Bolotov D.A. Vernon G. 2013.).

Thus, in order to prevent the occurrence of complications in patients with primary and recurrent mild degree of brain damage, clinical-neurological examinations and diagnostic methods of optimization, drawing up a treatment algorithm, can become worse for many of the above problems.

Keywords: Clinical and Neurological Manifestations, Repeated Mild Traumatic, Brain Injury, Comparative Analysis,

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The purpose of the study. Clinically proven clinical-neurological properties and method of treatment of mild to moderate head injury with mild to moderate head injury.

1. To study the frequency of repeated head and brain injuries.
2. To determine the clinical and neurological characteristics of mild degree of brain injury.
3. Comparison of clinical course of primary recurrent brain injury.
4. To evaluate the direct results of treatment of recurrent brain injury.

It is planned to examine, treat and compare the results obtained in two groups of 64 patients who received mild degree of brain injury (brain injury and mild degree of brain concussion) in the Buxoro District of Buxoro region for 2020-2021 years with mild degree of brain concussion (brain concussion and mild degree of concussion) in the age range 25-51.

To Group 1: 30 patients who received a mild degree of head injury in the first marotaba.(50%)

To Group 2: 30 patients (50%) with a mild degree of recurrent brain injury are scheduled for analysis.

That:

- 8 patients(27%) who received repeated brain damage within 1-3 months.
- 10 patients (33%) who received repeated brain damage within 3-6 months.
- 12 patients(40%) who received repeated brain damage within 1 year and more.

Both groups of patients undergo clinical and neurological examinations and undergo conservative treatments.

Intrascopic diagnostic methods included primary neuro-screening and expert assessment of structural intracranial changes (CT, MRI). For neuroscience and monitoring we used standard ultrasonography (US) of the infant brain for children with an open fontanel and transcranial US (TUS) for children with a closed fontanel. CT/MRI was performed depending on the results of the primary clinicsonographic evaluation. Statistical methods. Descriptive statistics (determination of the arithmetic mean with calculation of the standard error of the mean value) and mathematical statistics were used. The degree of consistency of neuroimaging techniques (US, CT, MRI) was determined using the kappa coefficient (kw): values exceeding 0.66 indicated high consistency of estimates, values in the range of 0.55-0.40 indicated a value in the range from good to noticeable consistency, less than 0.30 indicated weak consistency. In the course of clinical and sonographic assessment of the neurological condition of patients, the diagnostic effectiveness of US and the prevalence of SVI were studied. Statistical decisions in data analysis were made at a 5% significance level. Calculations were carried out using the SPSS 13 software package. General characteristics of the group: n=64, aged from the newborn period to 18 years; the average age of the victims. Depending on the type of treatment received, the victims were divided into group II (A) — 34

children released home for outpatient treatment and group II (B, C) — 30 victims who received inpatient treatment.

CONCLUSIONS: In the work of the scientific examination, clinical, neurological and instrumental examinations are performed to prevent early or late neurological changes that may develop in patients with primary and recurrent brain injuries. With the obtained indicators compared among themselves, the variants of the development of various types of clinical and neurological complications of head injuries with a slight degree of recurrence are studied. To determine the clinical and neurological characteristics of a mild degree of brain damage and to study the frequency of repeated head and brain injuries can prevent the development of complications.

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